

Performance of SHG - Bank Linkage Programme : A Regional Analysis

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Sonam

Research Scholar
Commerce
M.M.H College
Ghaziabad,Uttar Pradesh, India,

Abhishek Kumar Singh

Assistant Professor
Commerce
MMH College, Ghaziabad
Uttar Pradesh, India

Inamur Rahaman

Assistant Professor
Commerce
MMH College, Ghaziabad
Uttar Pradesh, India

Abstract

Even today, many people in our country are living below the poverty line. Regularly, Efforts are being made to bring this deprived class into the mainstream through microfinance. Through these, people are being empowered by income generation, financial assistance, skill development etc. so that they can fulfill their basic necessities and contribute to the development of the society. One such effort is the SHG-Bank Linkage Program started by NABARD in the year 1992. Through this, people's dependence on informal sources of credit was reduced and loans were provided to them by the bank so that they could get rid of the never-ending loans from informal sources. This program has brought positive results in the field of women empowerment in society as well as in financial independency. In this study, region-wise analysis of the performance of SHGs in terms of savings, loan disbursement and outstanding loan amount has been done. The analysis is based on the data published in the report "Status of Microfinance Programme in India" released annually by NABARD. The period from 2013-14 to 2022-23 has been considered for the study. In this study, mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation and compound annual growth rate have been calculated for analysis. One way ANOVA has been used to check the statistical significance. After analysis, it has come out that the effect of SHG-Bank Linkage Program is different in all regions. And this difference is in the context of savings, loan disbursed and outstanding loan.

Keywords Self Help Group, Microfinance, SHG- Bank Linkage, Progress Report, Poverty Eradication, Rural Development, Growth of SHG.

Introduction

Microfinance has been widely accepted as a means of eradicate poverty. Self Help Group (SHG) programme has also emerged as an important step under micro finance. In the year 1984, the concept of SHGs came up based on the Grameen Bank model of Prof. Mohd. Yunus. Self Help Group (SHG) plays an important role in many important issues affecting the poor society. SHG is a group of 10-25 members. Its members are generally people from similar social and economic backgrounds who voluntarily make small investments. When needed, members take loans from SHGs from their collective savings and from banks. Collective pressure of group works for repayment of the loan. SHGs provide collateral free loans which play a very important role in protecting members from informal sources of loans. Apart from this, the group also regularly makes efforts for skill development of the members. Apart from savings and loans, SHGs provide a platform to its members that helps people to come together and take important steps collectively on issues of health and socio-economic importance. They can solve their issues and problems through self-help and community action. They help their members in self-employment through savings and loan activities.

SHG-Bank Linkage Programme is working as an effective mechanism for the poor and deprived people. This programme was started in the year 1992 with 500 groups to link the groups with formal financial sources. Due to its effectiveness, this programme has become

one of the important microfinance programmes in the world with a large customer base. By conducting regular group meetings, collecting savings regularly, providing loans, repaying loans on time and maintaining the accounts of the groups regularly, these groups are progressing towards regular development. Thus, the groups have emerged as good customers of the bank. Various organisations are also playing an important role as promoting organisations of the groups. They help in organising, nurturing the self-help groups and enabling credit linkage with banks. As most of the groups are exclusively women groups, the programme also promotes women empowerment in the country. NABARD has strengthened the implementation of SHGs through various policies. NABARD also provides refinance assistance to banks for providing finance to the SHGs.

The success of microfinance depends on the quality of the SHGs and its smooth functioning. This is why SHGs are considered the core element of microfinance. Some of the basic working principles and functions of SHG are:

1. SHGs regularly contribute from their small savings to create a common fund.
2. These groups are managed democratically. That is, all members participate in the decisions of the group.
3. Loan requests are approved by a collective committee of all.
4. Loans are provided after completing some common formalities without any collateral.
5. The loan amount is small and its tenure is also short, the group usually has information about the use of the loan funds.
6. The collective pressure of the members reduces the default in the loan repayment.

According to the report of the SHG, the bank linkage programme started with 500 SHGs to eradicate poverty by providing financial assistance.

SHGs are supported and trained by NGOs, banks and institutions that promoting self-help groups. Apart from these, SHGs, which are working as the most prominent model of microfinance in India, are also promoted by Regional Rural Banks, State Governments and MFIs. They provide both group and individual loans. SHGs are also emerging as community platforms from where women can play an active role in women-centric issues. This develops self-confidence in them, so that they can take action against domestic violence, dowry harassment, abuse of women. The aim of the Millennium Development Goals is to eliminate poverty, improve education and health, protect the environment, and enhance other aspects of human welfare. The role of SHGs are also emerging in this regard. Various studies have discussed the positive changes that came in the lives of rural poor women after joining SHGs.

Objective of study

To analyse the extent of Self Help Group Bank Linkage Programme across all regions of India.

Review of Literature

S. Ravi and Dr. Vikkraman(2012) examined in a research study that Banks and other institutions that support self-help groups are financial aid or micro-loan providers for those people who are really economically backward in the society. Increasing number of poor women in our country are taking advantage of many new opportunities for their livelihood by joining self-help groups. And they remain active as group members by saving regularly. Due to their participation, managerial skills and literacy level of the members improve. Self-help groups have proved to be effective for the poor and weaker sections of the society.

J. Shirisha, K. Uma Devi & S. Suchiritha Devi(2021) concluded in their research the impact of SHGs on improving economic health, skill development and empowerment of households. Positive impact of rural development can be seen through Self Help Groups. SHGs have been used by governments, NGOs and others across the world to empower poor and backward people and enable them to fulfil their basic needs. In our country thousands of poor and marginalized population are getting benefited with various livelihood opportunities through Self Help Groups.

Paul Anand,Swati Saxena & Rolando Gozalez(2019) investigated in their study that SHG has shown that self-help group can be used to improve many levels of poverty alleviation and empowerment. Self-help-group program is not only a microfinance program but it also increases awareness along with skill development, health and nutrition education. The results have also been seen in the improvement in the standard of living of the self-help group members.

Sonali Chouhan & Neeta Maheshwari explore in her research study that Self Help Groups have become a successful system because of the key stakeholders, and as per the statistics more than 85% of Self Help Groups are run by them, they are playing a vital role in the development of society at large. Financial inclusion and bank linkage programmes make it possible to reach the services at the grassroot level. Which eliminates the informal sources of lenders. Positive changes are being brought in the society through Self Help Groups. And it is also being confirmed that if women are given opportunities for economic development, then they can join the mainstream.

Purna Chandra Parida And Anushree Sinha find out in their study that the performance and sustainability of three different types of SHGs and concludes that women SHGs are performing better than other types of SHGs. There are several reasons for this result. Women SHGs are functioning well by maintaining books of accounts, conducting savings and holding meetings regularly.

Methodology

For this study, secondary data has been used. This is mainly based on the report "Status of Micro Finance Program in India" that released by NABARD every year. For this study, the reports of the last ten years (2013-14 to 2022-23) have been analyzed. In this study, Mean, Standard Deviation, Co-Variance and ANOVA have been used for the analysis. The data is also collected from various sources like newspapers, magazines, websites, etc.

Analysis

Progress of SHGs savings with banks region wise for the period (2013-14 to 2022-23)

Table 1.1 shows the savings of SHGs deposited with banks from 2013-14 to 2022-23. This table shows the data of both number of SHGs and saving amount. As per the data shown in the table, the total CAGR growth rate for the last 10 years is 6.08% in number of SHGs and 19.52% in saving amount. Apart from this, analysis also shows that the northern region has the lowest CAGR for saving amount at 15.78% and the eastern region has the highest CAGR at 27.57%. The first part of the table shows the compound growth rate of number of SHGs. According to which the eastern region has the highest growth rate of 10.34% and the southern region has the lowest CAGR of 1.12%. From this, it can be concluded that the eastern region is working more efficiently in reference of savings with banks. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to find out whether the difference is statistically significant or not. As per the ANOVA results in Table 1.2, the value of F is greater than the critical value of F for both savings amount and no. of SHGs links with savings with banks. The significance level is kept at 5%. As per the result, the null hypotheses for both number of SHGs and amount of savings are rejected. From this, it can be concluded that the performance of all the regions is different in terms of savings.

Table 1.1 :Progress of SHGs savings with banks region wise during the period (2013-14 to 2022-23)

	Sr. no.	Year	Northern	Neastern	Eastern	Central	Western	Southern	Total
	1	2013-14	365208	316299	1468786	685929	896954	3696324	7429500
	2	2014-15	11018	5254	36098	33591	72704	274498	433163
	3	2015-16	393475	429823	1700106	815653	1018049	3545896	7903002
	4	2016-17	457199	452887	1953076	848514	1140601	3724598	8576875
	5	2017-18	478883	485591	2130997	902222	1097448	3649296	8744437
	6	2018-19	548624	523469	2654358	1062759	1388615	3836418	10014243
	7	2019-20	577122	556899	2811130	1135083	1473853	3689236	10243323
	8	2020-21	609808	633714	3122424	1345575	1550176	3961703	11223400
	9	2021-22	680143	680845	3243980	1355564	4244070	1688451	11893053
	10	2022-23	787807	793320	3930551	1832040	1927560	4131805	13403083
	Mean		490928.7	487810.1	2305151	1001693	1481003	3219823	8986408
	S.D		212322.9	217254.3	1102406	478350.8	1087763	1237170	3536760
	C.V		0.432492	0.445367	0.478236	0.477542	0.734477	0.384235	0.393568
	CAGR		7.991098	9.631425	10.3442	10.32288	7.95028	1.119981	6.077802
No. of SHGs	Sr. no.	Year	Northern	Neastern	Eastern	Central	Western	Southern	Total
	1	2013-14	28294.76	12882.12	152655.6	79055.81	92990.9	623862.4	989741.5
	2	2014-15	1288.17	202.98	4766.25	5201.53	22940.89	72780.94	107180.8
	3	2015-16	45014.04	19026.33	248351.8	84108.67	105703.9	866934.3	1369139
	4	2016-17	49676.28	22955.7	336538.6	83898.12	138696.3	979657.7	1611423
	5	2017-18	49293.91	32207.59	441803.2	95385.11	124694.9	1215827	1959212
	6	2018-19	62452.82	40407.05	601154.9	133230	205275.2	1289928	2332448
	7	2019-20	59549.73	48140.55	664332.7	171217	201880.1	1470085	2615205
	8	2020-21	174344.8	83126.03	774912.4	211869.8	374023.2	2129485	3747761
	9	2021-22	199582.3	106440.9	1358595	325695.6	327690.7	2406043	4724048
	10	2022-23	122484.9	127152.8	1742499	458675.2	541610.6	2896845	5889268
	Mean		79198.17	49254.21	632561	164833.7	213550.7	1395145	2534543
	S.D		64705.24	42413.58	545427.3	135892.8	157269.6	860250.3	1775987
	C.V		0.817004	0.861116	0.862252	0.824424	0.736451	0.616603	0.700713
	CAGR		15.78109	25.72854	27.56925	19.2222	19.2682	16.596	19.52368
Saving Amount	Sr. no.	Year	Northern	Neastern	Eastern	Central	Western	Southern	Total
	1	2013-14	28294.76	12882.12	152655.6	79055.81	92990.9	623862.4	989741.5
	2	2014-15	1288.17	202.98	4766.25	5201.53	22940.89	72780.94	107180.8
	3	2015-16	45014.04	19026.33	248351.8	84108.67	105703.9	866934.3	1369139
	4	2016-17	49676.28	22955.7	336538.6	83898.12	138696.3	979657.7	1611423
	5	2017-18	49293.91	32207.59	441803.2	95385.11	124694.9	1215827	1959212
	6	2018-19	62452.82	40407.05	601154.9	133230	205275.2	1289928	2332448
	7	2019-20	59549.73	48140.55	664332.7	171217	201880.1	1470085	2615205
	8	2020-21	174344.8	83126.03	774912.4	211869.8	374023.2	2129485	3747761
	9	2021-22	199582.3	106440.9	1358595	325695.6	327690.7	2406043	4724048
	10	2022-23	122484.9	127152.8	1742499	458675.2	541610.6	2896845	5889268
	Mean		79198.17	49254.21	632561	164833.7	213550.7	1395145	2534543
	S.D		64705.24	42413.58	545427.3	135892.8	157269.6	860250.3	1775987
	C.V		0.817004	0.861116	0.862252	0.824424	0.736451	0.616603	0.700713
	CAGR		15.78109	25.72854	27.56925	19.2222	19.2682	16.596	19.52368

Table: 1.2 Hypothesis testing :- Savings of SHGs with banks

Variables	No. of SHGs linked with savings	Saving amount
f statistics	16.65077621	14.98895084
p-value	0.0000000006362544935	0.0000000032339544

inference	Rejected	Rejected
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Progress of Loan disbursed to SHGs during the period (2013-14 to 2022-23)

Table 2.1 shows the total loans disbursed to the SHGs by the banks during the study period of ten years . It shows both the number of SHGs and the amount of loans. As per the calculation of CAGR done here, the highest rate in terms of number of SHGs is of neastern region with 22.53% and lowest rate is of Southern region with 7.96%. The rate of neastern region is higher than the national average of 12.13% and that of Southern region is much lower. The second part of the table shows the growth in terms of amount of loan disbursed. Here again, the rate of neastern region was highest with 37.68% and the lowest rate is of Southern region with 16.53%. The combined rate of all the regions for the study period was 19.71%. ANOVA has been used for statistical significance of loan disbursement in all regions. As per Table 2.1, the value of F is greater than the critical value of F for 5% level of significance. Based on this, null hypothesis is rejected for both loan disbursed amount and no. of SHGs related to Loan disbursed amount . This shows that all regions have performed differently in terms of loan disbursement.

Table:2.1 Progress of Bank loan disbursed to SHGs region wise during the period (2013-14 to 2022-23)

Sr. no.	Year	Northern	Neastern	Eastern	Central	Western	Southern	Total
1	2013-14	23918	16201	297478	66393	87846	874585	1366421
2	2014-15	525	293	2825	2957	6094	92495	105189
3	2015-16	38106	26037	412576	84282	112525	1158797	1832323
4	2016-17	46567	28961	497063	82012	106825	1136692	1898120
5	2017-18	51800	35017	720444	69295	128973	1255603	2261132
6	2018-19	55922	27086	909375	85135	146674	1474208	2698400
7	2019-20	62905	37807	1123517	111074	174218	1636481	3146002
8	2020-21	67658	68116	1124578	128617	161159	1337266	2887394
9	2021-22	79532	94871	1301505	184322	239086	1498951	3398267
10	2022-23	102931	123602	1634604	278359	273253	1882772	4295521
	Mean	52986.4	45799.1	802396.5	109244.6	143665.3	1234785	2388877
	S.D	28640.68	38167.19	506206.4	75491.16	75814.89	490946.5	1173754
	C.V	0.540529	0.833361	0.630868	0.691029	0.527719	0.397597	0.491341
No. of SHGs	CAGR	15.71299	22.53167	18.57572	15.41129	12.01709	7.969122	12.1355

Sr. no.	Year	Northern	Neastern	Eastern	Central	Western	Southern	Total
1	2013-14	28048.36	12819.04	151067.2	61806.9	86443.65	206155.1	2401736
2	2014-15	529.33	356.45	2440.61	2906.85	7256.91	173664.6	187154.7
3	2015-16	48297.94	21968.7	349489	119066.7	188632.2	3001235	3728690
4	2016-17	57414.19	28420.67	473171	67958.46	148818.6	3102332	3878115
5	2017-18	54038.62	35721.73	908949.9	55943.55	155099.7	3508834	4718588
6	2018-19	62663.6	29001.21	1197079	72199.35	184563.9	4286256	5831763
7	2019-20	84693.71	57893.03	1785075	104249.5	249327.1	5484696	7765935
8	2020-21	94045.16	103650.7	1487551	105428.1	230330.6	3786063	5807068
9	2021-22	117102.2	184636.3	2568978	216983.2	381363.1	6503860	9972923
10	2022-23	206436.9	313764.1	3338333	463672.7	675144.2	9522672	14520023
Mean		75327	78823.19	1226213	127021.5	230698	4143116	5881199
S.D		56635.31	98924.49	1092168	130672.9	184882	2567737	4075097
C.V		0.751859	1.255018	0.890683	1.028746	0.801403	0.61976	0.692902
Loan Amount CAGR		22.09222	37.68124	36.2812	22.32563	22.81922	16.53503	19.7138

Table:-2.2 Hypothesis testing – Loan disbursed to SHGs

Variables	No. of SHGs linked loan disbursed	Loan disbursed amount
f statistics	29.46922725	19.84956278
p-value	0	0
inference	Rejected	Rejected

Progress of outstanding loans on SHGs during the period (2013-14 to 2022-23)

Table 3.1 shows the amount of loan outstanding and no. of SHGs related to these outstanding loans region wise for the period 2013-14 to 2022-23. It is evident from the table that the rate of outstanding loans has decreased in Northern region with negative CAGR whereas the number of SHGs with outstanding loans has increased in Eastern region with CAGR 9.3%. The CAGR of all regions in number of SHGs related to outstanding loans across the country is 5.18%. Further, CAGR in terms of outstanding loan amount is lowest in Central region with 6.6% and highest in Eastern with 23.24%. The combined CAGR of all regions for outstanding loan amount is 15.92%. When analysis done by using ANOVA to test the statistical significance it shows that the calculated values of F for both the number of SHGS as well as the amount of outstanding loans of these groups are greater than the critical value of F. The null hypothesis is rejected at

the level of significance at 5%. Thus, it can be concluded that all the regions performed differently in terms of outstanding loans.

Table:-3.1 Progress of loan outstanding on SHGs during the period (2013-14 to 2022-23)

No. of SHGs	Sr. no.	Year	Northern	Neastern	Eastern	Central	Western	Southern	Total
	1	2013-14	183929	124569	978960	419834	269008	2221038	4197338
	2	2014-15	6226	1239	20966	17319	37120	235389	318259
	3	2015-16	154724	150860	1130902	434797	258119	2543219	4672621
	4	2016-17	143905	143222	1343296	398411	278097	2541356	4848287
	5	2017-18	144428	143648	1412153	404378	276336	2639415	5020358
	6	2018-19	124130	123554	1690515	324142	276901	2538090	5077332
	7	2019-20	133515	131006	1955112	354466	284109	2818863	5677071
	8	2020-21	143275	164421	2252039	368271	312913	2539325	5780244
	9	2021-22	161848	212009	2459218	407004	391082	3108796	6739957
	10	2022-23	170971	268593	2383255	495999	429237	3208996	6957051
Mean		136695.1	146312.1	1562642	362462.1	281292.2	2439449	4928852	
S.D		49113.07	68235.81	752589.3	129991.1	102908.4	828023.9	1843114	
C.V		0.359289	0.466372	0.481613	0.358634	0.365842	0.339431	0.373944	
CAGR		-0.7279	7.986253	9.305133	1.68112	4.783571	3.748379	5.182896	
Loan outstanding Amount	Sr. no.	Year	Northern	Neastern	Eastern	Central	Western	Southern	Total
	1	2013-14	110063.6	75379.91	494463.1	269666.5	164046.1	3179133	4292752
	2	2014-15	4394.5	790.59	13821	16644.83	18097.67	292513.1	346261.7
	3	2015-16	115907	88472.73	703766.6	289590	203461.6	4310725	5711923
	4	2016-17	91167.07	83160.29	888561.6	221368.6	208907.8	4664965	6158130
	5	2017-18	86864.6	89048.4	1168064	216172	237207.3	5762489	7559845
	6	2018-19	99374.38	83132.07	1652544	200443.1	246800.4	6427521	8709815
	7	2019-20	122215.5	103194.6	2276461	225097.1	303111.2	7777427	10807507
	8	2020-21	123034.1	144455.5	2594652	252282	328785.5	6885762	10328971
	9	2021-22	165377.8	236245.1	3529425	325178.4	449276.6	10399627	15105130
	10	2022-23	209750.3	390420.1	3997045	512131	687851.1	13010683	18807880
Mean		112814.9	129429.9	1731880	252857.4	284754.5	6271084	8782822	
S.D		53173.66	109291.4	1332433	122808.3	180606.7	3607449	5334583	
C.V		0.471335	0.844406	0.769356	0.485682	0.634254	0.575251	0.607388	
CAGR		6.661061	17.87662	23.2425	6.624107	15.4125	15.13282	15.92054	

Table:-3.2 Hypothesis testing – Loan outstanding

Variables	No. of SHGs linked with	Outstanding loan amount
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	outstanding loan	
f statistics	42.85277946	23.9523348
p-value	0	0
inference	Rejected	Rejected

Conclusion In the national interest , the main goal of policy makers is to removing inequalities. Inequalities exist in the country in various geographical, socio-economic forms. Special attention is given by policy makers to the economic inequalities so that social and livelihood opportunities can be provided to all the people. In this way, continuous efforts are being made by the government to remove regional inequalities. So that the nation can develop along with balanced regional development. This research paper has found that positive results have come out in terms of savings, loan disbursement and loan outstanding through the SHG-BLP program. Its analysis results show that positive trend is seen in the context of SHGs related to saving amount in the 10-year study period. Apart from this, positive trends have also come out in terms of loan distribution. Finally, CAGR also shows positive trend in terms of outstanding loan. Region wise performance is different in terms of all three aspects. Thus, using ANOVA test, it has also been found that there are significant differences in terms of these three aspects in different regions. Thus, SHG-Bank program has shown different performance region wise in the field of microfinance but it is taking people towards economic prosperity by providing them financial assistance.

References

1. Amutha, D. (n.d.). *Socio-Economic Impact through Self Help Groups*. www.iiste.org.
2. Anand, P., Saxena, S., Gonzalez, R., & Dang, H.-A. H. (2019). *Can Women's Self-Help Groups Contribute to Sustainable Development? Evidence of Capability Changes from Northern India*. <http://www.worldbank.org/prwp>.
3. Bali Swain, R., & Varghese, A. (2009). *The Impact of Skill Development and Human Capital Training on Self Help Groups*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228425185>
4. Chandra, P., And, P., & Sinha, A. (2010). *Performance and Sustainability of Self-Help Groups in India: A Gender Perspective*. In *Asian Development Review* (Vol. 27, Issue 1)
5. Chouhan, S., Maheshwari, N (2021). *The Growth of Self Help Groups in India-A Critical Study*. 23(9), 12–17 <https://doi.org/10.9790/487X-2309031217>
6. Dutta, B. (2015a). *Rural Development Through Selp Help Groups (Shgs): An Overview*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341965198>
7. Junuthula, S., Uma, K., Shirisha, J., Uma Devi, K., & Suchiritha Devi Professor, S. (2021). *A REVIEW ON SELF HELP GROUPS-FINANCIAL INCLUSION PROGRAMME AND ITS IMPACT IN INDIA*.
8. Kumar Minz, N. K. (n.d.). *Impact of Microfinancing and Self-Help Groups (SHGs) on Women's Empowerment*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8416412>
9. Seetharaman, K., Priyakumari, S. v, & Karthik, S. (2017). *Impact of Self Help Group in Economic Empowerment of Rural Women-A Study*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338902483>
10. *The Growth of Self Help Groups in India: A Study*. (n.d.). <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/291350535>
11. *MINISTRY OF RURAL DEVELOPMENT GOVERNMENT OF INDIA Outcome of SHG Bank Linkage Project Outcome of SHG Bank Linkage Project*. <https://rural.gov.in/en/press-release/outcome-shg-bank-linkage-project>

Reports

1. National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD).(2013-14).*Status of Microfinance Programme in India 2013-14. Mumbai,India*
2. National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD).(2014-15).*Status of Microfinance Programme in India 2014-15. Mumbai,India*
3. National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD).(2015-16).*Status of Microfinance Programme in India 2015-16.. Mumbai,India*
4. National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD).(2016-17).*Status of Microfinance Programme in India 2016-17. Mumbai,India*
5. National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD).(2017-18).*Status of Microfinance Programme in India 2017-18. Mumbai,India*
6. National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD).(2018-19).*Status of Microfinance Programme in India 2018-19. Mumbai,India*
7. National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD).(2019-20).*Status of Microfinance Programme in India 2019-20. Mumbai,India*

8. National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD).(2020-21).*Status of Microfinance Programme in India 2020-21. Mumbai,India*
9. National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD).(2021-22).*Status of Microfinance Programme in India 2021-22. Mumbai,India*
10. National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD).(2022-23).*Status of Microfinance Programme in India 2022-23. Mumbai,Indi*